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Preventing Recalcitrant **O**rganic **M**obile Industrial chemicals for **C**ircular Economy in the soil-sediment-water **S**ystem

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D6.10 – PROMISCES CEN Workshop Business Plan

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Executive Summary

The deliverable “D6.10 CEN Workshop Business Plan” provides the structured framework for the establishment and management of a CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA), ensuring that the Workshop operates effectively, engages relevant stakeholders, and ultimately achieves its intended goals in the development of documents.

The CEN Workshop Business Plan outlines the objectives and scope of the planned CWA focused on Persistent, Mobile, and Toxic (PMT) substances and per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS). The Business Plan is a collaborative effort involving three sister projects from the Green Deal Call (topic 8.1), PROMISCES, ZeroPM, and SCENARIOS. The primary goals of the CWA are to address challenges related to PMT substances in soil, sediment, and water systems, covering prevention, detection, risk assessment, and remediation. Key points include the development of methods for PFAS analysis, risk assessment improvements, and solutions for PFAS removal from various matrices like wastewater, sediment, and sludge. The CWA aims to promote circular economy routes and is relevant to researchers, public authorities, water utilities, and solution-developing companies.

The next steps in the CWA process will involve the convening of discussions and the eventual drafting of the CWA document based on the framework presented in this Business Plan.

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1 Introduction

This deliverable contains the draft CEN Workshop Business Plan on "Soil-sediment-water system - Solutions to deal with PMT/vPvM substances" to be submitted for CEN approval. It also includes the CEN Workshop Proposal Form which was submitted to the CEN-CENELEC Director Standardization for allocation to a CEN-CENELEC Management Centre (CCMC) Project Manager and is currently under review. To put the Business Plan into context, the aim and topic of this CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA) will be outlined as well as the role of the CEN Workshop Business Plan, its structure and importance of a CWA for the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities in the framework of the PROMISCES project.

1.1 The CWA process

The CWA is a collaborative document developed within the European Committee for Standardization (CEN) framework. CWAs serve as consensus-based guidelines, best practices, or solutions to address specific challenges or needs. They are particularly valuable in addressing emerging issues where formal European standards may not exist, or where more flexible and rapid development of guidance is required.

The PROMISCES project has initiated this CWA with the aim to consolidate solutions for managing (very) persistent, (very) mobile, and toxic (PMT/vPvM) substances in the soil-sediment-water system. This is essential due to the pressing environmental and health risks posed by substances like per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS). The CWA will provide strategies and best practices for detection, risk assessment, remediation, and prevention of PMT substances, benefiting a wide range of stakeholders, including researchers, public authorities, water utilities, and companies.

The complete CWA process is shown in Figure 1. As a first step, the Proposal Form (see Annex 2) was prepared together with the collaborating national CEN member (DIN – Deutsches Institut für Normung e.V.). The Proposal Form gives a quick review of the main aspects of the planned CWA and was coordinated within the PROMISCES consortium and with the interested sister projects ZeroPM and SCENARIOS. It was submitted by the DIN and is currently under review. Based on the Proposal Form, a draft of the CEN Workshop Business Plan (see Annex 1) was developed. It will be open for commenting (Step 3, Figure 1) as soon as the Proposal Form has been approved by CEN, allowing participants the opportunity to review and provide comments. The Business Plan serves as the roadmap for the creation and execution of a CWA. The preliminary draft included in this deliverable will be the subject of extensive discussion during the CWA kick-off meeting, establishing a structured framework for the development of the CWA.

Figure 1: The CWA process contains several steps starting with the submission of the Proposal Form, the development of a project (former: business) plan, followed by the development of the CWA, starting with the Kick-off meeting.¹

1.2 Structure of the Draft Business Plan

The Draft Business Plan (now called a Project Plan) begins by detailing the current status of the project plan, providing information about the participation requests and the date of the workshop kick-off meeting on February 15, 2024. The next section lists the workshop proposer and potential participants, including two sister research projects funded by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme – ZeroPM and SCENARIOS. The workshop's openness to interested parties is underlined, including academic and research institutions, standards application experts, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), manufacturers, test institutes, public sector representatives, research institutes specializing in environmental issues, and solution providers in the field of PMT management. This leads to a section that focuses on the CEN workshop's objectives and scope, highlighting its background and the need for addressing challenges related to PMT/vPvM substances. The resource planning section discusses funding and administrative aspects, specifying that administrative costs are covered by the PROMISCES project, while participants are responsible for their own expenses. The text then explains the rules and procedures governing participation in the workshop, decision-making processes, and the roles of the Workshop Chair and Workshop Secretariat in the workshop structure. Lastly, the dissemination and participation strategy details the

¹ Source: [CEN/CENELEC Workshop Project Plan](#)

plan for communicating information about the workshop, including the proposal form submission, open commenting period, and CWA publication to relevant stakeholders and the public.

In summary, this Draft Business Plan comprehensively outlines the context, structure, and objectives of the CWA for addressing PMT/vPvM substances in the soil-sediment-water system. It highlights its significance in dealing with critical environmental and health challenges, and provides insights into the planned schedule, resource allocation, and rules of cooperation for workshop participants, reflecting the collaborative and inclusive nature of the CEN Workshop Agreement, which aims to engage a broad range of stakeholders in addressing pressing issues.

1.3 The CWA as tool for communication, dissemination and exploitation

The CWA plays a crucial role in the communication, dissemination, and exploitation of project results. It will document project results and solutions in a standardized and easily understandable manner, providing a well-defined structure and a common language for conveying technical information, promoting effective communication among diverse stakeholders, including researchers, public authorities, businesses, and the general public. The clear presentation of best practices and solutions within the CWA will simplify the understanding and discussion among stakeholders. Furthermore, the CWA will be published and made accessible to the public, facilitating the widespread dissemination of the developed solutions and best practices. Individuals and organizations working on similar challenges can access the CWA, fostering the adoption of best practices and innovation in related fields. Regarding exploitation, the CWA functions as a reference document that can serve as a basis for further work and developments related to the project's topic. It provides a summarized overview of the developed solutions and can serve as a starting point for the development of standards or guidelines.

In summary, the CWA contributes to effective communication of project results, enables their dissemination in a broad context, and provides a foundation for the evaluation and further development of the progress achieved. With a validity of three years, the CWA is a valuable tool to ensure that project efforts are not only beneficial during their duration but also have long-term impacts and applications.

2 Annex 1: CWA Draft Business Plan

**Draft Project plan for the CEN
Workshop on "Soil-sediment-
water system - Solutions to deal
with PMT/vPvM substances"**

**Requests to participate in the Workshop
and/or comments on the project plan are
to be submitted by
15th January 2024 to
madlen.schmudde@din.de²**

Recipients of this project plan are kindly requested
to name all patent rights known to them to be
relevant to the Workshop and to make available all
supporting documents.

Berlin, 13th October 2023 (Version 1.0)

² Applications for participating in the Workshop and comments on the project plan that are not received by the deadline do not need to be taken into consideration. Once constituted, the Workshop will decide whether or not to consider the comments received in good time.

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Summary

This CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA) is initiated to tackle the growing concerns surrounding (very) persistent, (very) mobile, and toxic (PMT/vPvM) substances, particularly focusing on per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), which pose significant environmental and health risks. The need for this workshop arises from the pressing challenges related to the detection, risk assessment, remediation, and prevention of PMT substances in the soil-sediment water system. The workshop aims to consolidate solutions from three research projects funded by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme – PROMISCES, ZeroPM, and SCENARIOS – benefitting a wide range of stakeholders, including researchers, public authorities, water utilities, and companies. The workshop focuses on circular economy strategies and aims to provide best practices and guidelines while not explicitly addressing the implementation or enforcement of standards.

1. Status of the project plan

Draft project plan for public commenting (Version 1.0)

This draft project plan is intended to inform the public of a new Workshop. Any interested party can take part in this Workshop and/or comment on this draft project plan. Please send any requests to participate or comments by e-mail to madlen.schmudde@din.de.

All those who have applied for participation or have commented on the project plan by the deadline will be invited to the kick-off meeting of the Workshop on **2024-02-15**.

2. Workshop proposer and Workshop participants

2.1. Workshop proposer

Person or organisation	Short description and interest in the subject
Name: Dr. Thomas Track Organization: DECHEMA Gesellschaft für Chemische Technik und Biotechnologie e.V. Postal address: Theodor-Heuss-Allee 25, 60486 Frankfurt am Main, Germany Email: thomas.track@dechema.de Phone: +49 69 7564-427 Webpage: www.dechema.de	Freshwater and wastewater expert with a focus on zero pollution, circularity approaches and soil-sediment-water resources management. He is strongly working on the interface of transferring new developments into application.

2.2. Other potential participants

This CWA will be developed in a Workshop (temporary body) that is open to any interested party. The participation of other experts would be helpful and is desired. It is recommended that:

- Academic and Research Institutions
- Standards Application Experts
- Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs)
- Manufacturers of PMT-related products
- Test Institutes for PMT substances
- Representatives of the Public Sector
- Research Institutes specializing in environmental issues
- System/Solution Providers in the field of PMT management

take part in the development of this CWA.

2.3. Participants at the kick-off meeting

The following persons or organisations already signed up to the kick-off meeting prior to the publication of the draft project plan.

Person	Organisation
Workshop proposer: Dr. Thomas Track	DECHEMA Gesellschaft für chemische Technik und Biotechnologie e.V.
Dr. Julie Lions	BRGM, Bureau de recherches géologiques et minières
Dr. Veronika Zhitneva	KWB, Kompetenzzentrum Wasser Berlin gemeinnützige gmbh
Dr. Valeria Dulio	INERIS - Institut national de l'environnement et des risques
Dr. Anita Sosnowska	QSAR LAB – QSAR LAB spolka z ograniczona odpowiedzialnoscia
Jochen Kuckelkorn	UBA – Umweltbundesamt
Dr. Peter Behnisch	BDS - BioDetection Systems B.V.
Laura del Val	EURECAT - Fundacio Eurecat
Dr. Martine Bakker	RIVM - Rijksinstituut voor volksgezondheid en milieu
Miren López de Alda	CSIC - Agencia estatal consejo superior de investigaciones científicas
Thomas James Oudega	TU WIEN - Technische Universitaet Wien
Francesco Fatone	UNIVPM - Universita politecnica delle marche
María José Muñoz Muñoz	CBT - Consorci besos tordera
Ricard Mora	ESOLVE - Esolve consultoria e ingenieria medioambiental sl
Joana Baeta	ESOLVE - Esolve consultoria e ingenieria medioambiental sl
Evgenia Benova	UNISOFIA - Sofia University St Kliment Ohridski
Benjamin Laulier	SINAPTEC Ultrasonic technology
Zsuzsanna Nagy-Kovács	BUWW - fovarosi vizmuvek zartkoruen mukodoreszvenytarsasag
Frugis Alessandro	ACEA - ACEA engineering laboratories research innovation societa per azioni
Asci Maria Grazia	SIMAM - Simam spa simam s.p.a. Italy
Sarah Hale	TZW – Technologiezentrum Wasser
Mihaela Mirea	LOMARTOV
Workshop secretariat: Dr. Madlen Schmutde	DIN e.V.

3. Workshop objectives and scope

3.1. Background

Over the past decades, concerns have been growing about chemicals which do not degrade ((very) persistent substances; (v)P), can easily spread throughout the aqueous environment ((very) mobile substances; (v)M) and are suspected to harm organisms (toxic substances; T). However, various challenges concerning the detection, risk assessment, remediation, and prevention of these PMT/vPvM substances from entering the soil-sediment-water system still exist and need to be addressed.

The Horizon 2020 research projects PROMISCES, ZeroPM and SCENARIOS all aim at developing solutions to meet these challenges. The planned CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA) is intended to present a collection of these solutions and is targeted at all stakeholders active in the field of PMT management, whether they are researchers, public authorities, problem owners, water utilities, soil/brownfield actors or companies developing market-ready solutions. The relevance for per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) is especially high as expected future EU legislations may demand that affected stakeholders address these substances, and they need the appropriate solutions to do this.

The **prevention of PFAS** from entering the soil-sediment-water system relies on a reduction in manufacture, use and release. Tools such as policy development, a stimulation towards safe and sustainable chemicals as well as the identification and use of alternatives are needed. Within ZeroPM, tools will be developed to allow companies to identify where they are using PFAS and databases will be produced for alternatives to these uses. Opportunities and constraints in current PFAS policy will be identified and exploited.

The **analysis of PFAS** is complicated due to their adsorption tendencies and high blank values. So far, no standardised methods for many PFAS substances and other emerging PMT/vPvMs exist, and these substances are not integrated into routine analysis due to specific methods required for detection. Within PROMISCES, methods will be developed for wastewaters, surface, ground- and drinking waters, and for complex solid matrices (such as sewage sludge, sediment, fertilizers, or stack emission). The methods and workflows will ensure maximum interlaboratory comparability. Within ZeroPM, analytical methods will be developed for certain PFAS parameters and testing methods will be verified for soil, water, and sludge.

Concerning **risk assessment**, crucial toxicological, persistence, and mobility data gaps exist. In vitro bioassay test batteries and in silico models are developed by PROMISCES to assess not only single substances but also to evaluate whole substance classes and complex (water) samples to fill these gaps for PMT/vPvM substances and thus, will also be addressed in the inventory. When assessing the risks for human health, the focus to date often lies on pathogens and non-threshold chemicals, while there are no standardized approaches for PMT/vPvMs. The developed solutions to improve risk assessment and facilitate optimal risk management and preventive solutions will be part of this CWA. ZeroPM will further contribute by considering both internal and external, human and environmental exposure in advanced risk assessment models.

Concerning **PFAS remediation**, the interest in new insights and technologies is high. Industrial sites contaminated by PFAS have been identified as primary sources responsible for groundwater contamination. PROMISCES results on a novel treatment train for contaminated soils and groundwater will also form part of the solutions inventory. In addition, wastewater can contain various PFAS at different concentrations. However, persistent PFAS are poorly removed in conventional Wastewater Treatment Plants which limits circularity in the water cycle, for instance by complicating nutrients recovery from sewage sludge for fertiliser use. Up to date recommendations on choosing sludge treatment technologies to deliver 'PFAS free' fertilisers are missing. There is also currently no mass flow analysis of PFAS fate and degradation during sediment treatment for material recovery from dredged sediments. Insights on PFAS removal from these matrices (i.e. wastewater, sediments, sludge) will be addressed in the CWA. PFAS removal from drinking water is also important to consider since urban areas with semi-closed water cycles face challenges posed by legacy pollutants and high chemical concentrations when providing sustainable drinking water. The results on combined drinking water treatment, as well as on advanced wastewater treatment and landfill leachate treatment can/will be addressed in the CWA.

ZeroPM will develop innovative solutions for water and sludge, looking at both removal efficiency but also sustainability metrics for the solutions. These results will inform risk management efforts.

3.2. Scope

The planned Workshop defines best practices, solutions, and guidelines concerning the handling of PMT/vPvM substances, not only assessing their behaviour in the soil-sediment water system but also their possible prevention at the source as well as end-of-pipe solutions. These solutions are clustered into categories (e.g. prevention, detection, risk assessment, measures) in order to reach various stakeholders within the system. As part of the categorized solutions, a special focus is placed on the following five circular economy routes:

1. Semi-closed water cycle for drinking water supply
2. Wastewater reuse for agricultural irrigation
3. Nutrient and energy recovery from treated sludge for fertilisers
4. Material recovery from dredged sediment for eco-materials
5. Groundwater and soil remediation to protect water cycle

The planned Workshop is applicable to researchers, public authorities, water utility operators, or companies developing market-ready solutions.

3.3. Related activities

The subject of the planned CWA is not at present the subject of a standard. However, there are committees, standards and/or other technical specifications that deal with related subjects and thus need to be taken into account - and involved, where necessary - during this Workshop:

- ISO/TC 147 – Water Quality
 - ISO 21675: Water quality - Determination of perfluoroalkyl and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) in water - Method using solid phase extraction and liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS)
- ISO/TC 190 - Soil quality
- ISO/TC 224 - Drinking water, wastewater and stormwater systems and services
- ISO/TC 275 - Sludge recovery, recycling, treatment and disposal
- ISO/TC 282 – Water reuse
- CEN/TC 230 - Water analysis
 - prEN 17892: Water quality - Determination of the sum of perfluorinated substances (Sum of PFAS) in drinking water - Method using liquid chromatography/mass spectrometry (LC/MS)
- CEN/TC 308 - Characterization and management of sludge
- CEN/TC 444 - Environmental characterization of solid matrices

4. Workshop programme

4.1. General

The kick-off meeting is planned to take place on 2024-02-15 virtually. A draft for public commenting will not be published.

A total of 6 Workshop meetings (kick-off meeting and Workshop meetings) and web conferences will be held, during which the content of the CWA will be presented, discussed and approved.

The CWA will be drawn up in **English** (language of meetings, minutes, etc.). The CWA will be written in **English**.

4.2. Workshop schedule

• **Table 1: Workshop schedule (preliminary)**

CEN/CENELEC Workshop	Oct 2023	Nov 2023	Dec 2023	Jan 2024	Feb 2024	Mar 2024	Apr 2024	May 2024	Jun 2024	Jul 2024	Aug 2024	Sep 2024	Oct 2024	Nov 2024
Initiation														
1. Proposal form submission and TC response														
2. Project plan development														
3. Open commenting period on draft project plan														
Operation														
4. Kick-off meeting														
5. CWA(s) development														
6. CWA(s) finalised and approved by Workshop participants														
Publication														
7. CWA(s) publication														
Dissemination														
Milestones														

- K** Kick-off
- V** Virtual Workshop meeting
- A** Adoption of CWA
- P** Publication of CWA
- D** Online distribution of CWA

4.3. Work already delivered

-

5. Resource planning

The administrative costs of the CEN Workshop will be covered by the PROMISCES (Preventing Recalcitrant Organic Mobile Industrial chemicals for Circular Economy in the Soil-sediment-water system) project, which received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036449.

All costs related to the participation of interested parties in the Workshop's activities have to be borne by themselves. The PROMISCES project aims to reach an agreement with CEN CENELEC Management Centre to make the CWA freely downloadable from the CEN Website. The copyright of the final CEN Workshop Agreement will be at CEN. The final document will include the following paragraph: "Results incorporated in this CEN Workshop Agreement received funding from the European Union's HORIZON 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101036449 (PROMISCES)".

6. Workshop structure and rules of cooperation

6.1. Participation in the Workshop

The Workshop will be constituted during the course of the kick-off meeting. By approving this project plan, the interested parties declare their willingness to participate in the Workshop and will be formally named as Workshop participants, with the associated rights and duties. Participants at the kick-off meeting who do not approve the project plan are not given the status of a Workshop participant and are thus excluded from further decisions made during the kick-off meeting and from any other decisions regarding the Workshop.

As a rule, the request to participate in the Workshop is closed once it is constituted. The current Workshop participants shall decide whether any additional members will be accepted or not.

Any new participant in the Workshop at a later date is decided on by the participants making up the Workshop at that time. It is particularly important to consider these aspects:

- a. expansion would be conducive to shortening the duration of the Workshop or to avoiding or averting an impending delay in the planned duration of the Workshop;
- b. the expansion would not result in the Workshop taking longer to complete;
- c. the new Workshop participant would not address any new or complementary issues beyond the scope defined and approved in the project plan;
- d. the new Workshop participant would bring complementary expertise into the Workshop in order to incorporate the latest scientific findings and state-of-the-art knowledge;
- e. the new Workshop participant would actively participate in the drafting of the manuscript by submitting concrete, not abstract, proposals and contributions;
- f. the new Workshop participant would ensure wider application of the CWA.

All Workshop participants who voted for the publication of the CWA or its draft will be named as authors in the European Foreword, including the organisations which they represent. All Workshop participants who voted against the publication of the CWA, or who have abstained, will not be named in the European Foreword.

6.2. Workshop responsibilities

The Workshop Chair is responsible for content management and any decision-making and voting procedures. The Workshop Chair is supported by the Workshop Vice-Chair and the responsible Workshop secretariat, whereby the Workshop secretariat will always remain neutral regarding the content of the CWA(s). Furthermore, the Workshop secretariat shall ensure that CEN-CENELEC's rules of procedure, rules of presentation, and the principles governing the publication of CWA(s) have been observed. Should a Workshop Chair no longer be able to carry out her/his duties, the Workshop secretariat shall initiate the election of a new Workshop Chair. The list below covers the main tasks of the Workshop Chair. It is not intended to be exhaustive.

- Content related contact point for the Workshop
- Presides at Workshop meetings
- Ensures that the development of the CWA respects the principles and content of the adopted project plan
- Manages the consensus building process, decides when the Workshop participants have reached agreement on the final CWA, on the basis of the comments received
- Ensures due information exchange with the Workshop secretariat
- Represents the Workshop and its results to exterior

The Workshop secretariat, provided by a CEN/CENELEC national member, is responsible for organising and leading the kick-off meeting, in consultation with the Workshop proposer. Further Workshop meetings and/or web conferences shall be organised by the Workshop secretariat in consultation with the Workshop Chair. The list below covers the main tasks of the Workshop secretariat. It is not intended to be exhaustive.

- Administrative and organisational contact point for the Workshop
- Ensures that the development of the CWA respects the principles and content of the adopted project plan and of the requirements of the CEN-CENELEC Guide 29
- Formally registers Workshop participants and maintains record of participating organisations and individuals
- Offers infrastructure and manage documents and their distribution through an electronic platform
- Prepares agenda and distribute information on meetings and meeting minutes as well as follow-up actions of the Workshop
- Initiates and manage CWA approval process upon decision by the Workshop Chair
- Interface with CEN-CENELEC Management Centre (CCMC) and Workshop Chair regarding strategic directions, problems arising, and external relationships
- Advises on CEN-CENELEC rules and bring any major problems encountered (if any) in the development of the CWA to the attention of CEN-CENELEC Management Centre (CCMC)
- Administrates the connection with relevant CEN or CENELEC/TCs

6.3. Decision making process

Each Workshop participant is entitled to vote and has one vote. If an organisation sends several experts to the Workshop, that organisation has only one vote, regardless of how many Workshop participants it sends. Transferring voting rights to other Workshop participants is not permitted. During voting procedures, decisions are passed by simple majority; abstentions do not count.

If Workshop participants cannot be present in the meetings when the CWA or its draft is adopted, an alternative means of including them in the voting procedure shall be used.

7. Dissemination and participation strategy

Proposal form submission

The Workshop proposal will be disseminated to the following relevant stakeholders and bodies for consultation:

- ISO/TC 147 – Water Quality
- ISO/TC 190 - Soil quality
- ISO/TC 224 - Drinking water, wastewater and stormwater systems and services
- ISO/TC 275 - Sludge recovery, recycling, treatment and disposal
- ISO/TC 282 – Water reuse
- CEN/TC 230 - Water analysis
- CEN/TC 308 - Characterization and management of sludge
- CEN/TC 444 - Environmental characterization of solid matrices
- CEN/TC 165 - Waste water engineering
- CEN/TC 260 - Fertilizers and liming materials
- CEN/TC 248 - Textiles and textile products

Open commenting period on draft project plan

In addition to the CCMC website, the project plan and the date of the kick-off meeting will be advertised on the website of the R&I project PROMISCES as well as by the partners to raise awareness. Interested parties are requested to

contribute either through commenting of the project plan (short term) or through Workshop participation (long term). The draft project plan will be disseminated to the following relevant stakeholders and bodies for consultation:

- ISO/TC 147 – Water Quality
- ISO/TC 190 - Soil quality
- ISO/TC 224 - Drinking water, wastewater and stormwater systems and services
- ISO/TC 275 - Sludge recovery, recycling, treatment and disposal
- ISO/TC 282 – Water reuse
- CEN/TC 230 - Water analysis
- CEN/TC 308 - Characterization and management of sludge
- CEN/TC 444 - Environmental characterization of solid matrices
- CEN/TC 165 - Waste water engineering
- CEN/TC 260 - Fertilizers and liming materials
- CEN/TC 248 - Textiles and textile products

CWA publication

The published CWA will be advertised on the website of the R&I project PROMISCES as well as by the partners to raise awareness. The published CWA will be advertised to the following relevant stakeholders and bodies for consultation:

- ISO/TC 147 – Water Quality
- ISO/TC 190 - Soil quality
- ISO/TC 224 - Drinking water, wastewater and stormwater systems and services
- ISO/TC 275 - Sludge recovery, recycling, treatment and disposal
- ISO/TC 282 – Water reuse
- CEN/TC 230 - Water analysis
- CEN/TC 308 - Characterization and management of sludge
- CEN/TC 444 - Environmental characterization of solid matrices
- CEN/TC 165 - Waste water engineering
- CEN/TC 260 - Fertilizers and liming materials
- CEN/TC 248 - Textiles and textile products

8. Contacts

- Workshop Secretariat:
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- Workshop proposer
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3 Annex 2: CWA Proposal Form

**Proposal for a CEN Workshop
on "Soil-sediment-water system
- Solutions to deal with
PMT/vPvM substances"**

1 Proposal Form for the Workshop proposer

Details of the Workshop proposer:

Name: Dr. Thomas Track
Organization: DECHEMA Gesellschaft für chemische Technik und Biotechnologie e.V.
Postal address: Theodor-Heuss-Allee 25, 60486 Frankfurt am Main, Germany
Email: thomas.track@dechema.de
Phone: +49 69 7564-427
Webpage: www.promisces.eu

Already known partners:

- Dr. Julie Lions, BRGM, Bureau de recherches géologiques et minières, PROMISCES
- Dr. Veronika Zhitneva KWB, Kompetenzzentrum Wasser Berlin gemeinnützige gmbh, PROMISCES
- Dr. Valeria Dulio, INERIS - Institut national de l'environnement et des risques, PROMISCES
- Dr. Anita Sosnowska, QSAR LAB – QSAR LAB spolka z ograniczona odpowiedzialnoscia, PROMISCES
- Jochen Kuckelkorn, UBA – Umweltbundesamt, PROMISCES
- Dr. Peter Behnisch, BDS - BioDetection Systems B.V., PROMISCES
- Laura del Val, EURECAT - Fundacio Eurecat, PROMISCES
- Dr. Martine Bakker, RIVM - Rijksinstituut voor volksgezondheid en milieu, PROMISCES
- Miren López de Alda, CSIC - Agencia estatal consejo superior de investigaciones científicas, PROMISCES
- Thomas James Oudega, TU WIEN - Technische universitaet wien, PROMISCES
- Francesco Fatone, UNIVPM - Universita politecnica delle marche, PROMISCES
- María José Muñoz Muñoz, CBT - Consorci besos tordera, PROMISCES
- Ricard Mora, Joana Baeta, ESOLVE - Esolve consultoria e ingenieria medioambiental sl, PROMISCES
- Evgenia Benova, UNISOFIA - Sofia University St Kliment Ohridski, Bulgaria, PROMISCES
- Benjamin Laulier, SINAPTEC Ultrasonic technology, PROMISCES
- Zsuzsanna Nagy-Kovács, BUWW - fovarosi vizmuvek zartkoruen mukodoreszvenytarsasag, PROMISCES
- Frugis Alessandro, ACEA - ACEA engineering laboratories research innovation societa per azioni, PROMISCES
- Asci Maria Grazia, SIMAM - Simam spa simam s.p.a. Italy, PROMISCES
- Sarah Hale, TZW – Technologiezentrum Wasser, ZeroPM project
- Mihaela Mirea, LOMARTOV, SCENARIOS project

Title of the proposed Workshop:

Soil-sediment-water system - Solutions to deal with PMT/vPvM substances

Background/Objectives:

Over the past decades, concerns have been growing about chemicals which do not degrade ((very) persistent substances; (v)P), can easily spread throughout the aqueous environment ((very) mobile substances; (v)M) and are suspected to harm organisms (toxic substances; T). However, various challenges concerning the detection, risk assessment, remediation, and prevention of these PMT/vPvM substances from entering the soil-sediment-water system still exist and need to be addressed.

The Horizon Europe research projects PROMISCES, ZeroPM and SCENARIOS all aim at developing solutions to meet these challenges. The planned CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA) is intended to present a collection of these solutions and is targeted at all stakeholders active in the field of PMT management, whether they are researchers, public authorities, problem owners, water utilities, soil/brownfield actors or companies developing market-ready solutions. The relevance for per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) is especially high as expected future EU legislations may demand that affected stakeholders address these substances, and they need the appropriate solutions to do this.

The **prevention of PFAS** from entering the soil-sediment-water system relies on a reduction in manufacture, use and release. Tools such as policy development, a stimulation towards safe and sustainable chemicals as well as the identification and use of alternatives are needed. Within ZeroPM, tools will be developed to allow

companies to identify where they are using PFAS and databases will be produced for alternatives to these uses. Opportunities and constraints in current PFAS policy will be identified and exploited.

The **analysis of PFAS** is complicated due to their adsorption tendencies and high blank values. So far, no standardised methods for many PFAS substances and other emerging PMT/vPvMs exist, and these substances are not integrated into routine analysis due to specific methods required for detection. Within PROMISCES, methods will be developed for wastewaters, surface, ground- and drinking waters, and for complex solid matrices (such as sewage sludge, sediment, fertilizers, or stack emission). The methods and workflows will ensure maximum interlaboratory comparability. Within ZeroPM, analytical methods will be developed for certain PFAS parameters and testing methods will be verified for soil, water, and sludge.

Concerning **risk assessment**, crucial toxicological, persistence, and mobility data gaps exist. In vitro bioassay test batteries and in silico models are developed by PROMISCES to assess not only single substances but also to evaluate whole substance classes and complex (water) samples to fill these gaps for PMT/vPvM substances and thus, will also be addressed in the inventory. When assessing the risks for human health, the focus to date often lies on pathogens and non-threshold chemicals, while there are no standardized approaches for PMT/vPvMs. The developed solutions to improve risk assessment and facilitate optimal risk management and preventive solutions will be part of this CWA. ZeroPM will further contribute by considering both internal and external, human and environmental exposure in advanced risk assessment models.

Concerning **PFAS remediation**, the interest in new insights and technologies is high. Industrial sites contaminated by PFAS have been identified as primary sources responsible for groundwater contamination. PROMISCES results on a novel treatment train for contaminated soils and groundwater will also form part of the solutions inventory. In addition, wastewater can contain various PFAS at different concentrations. However, persistent PFAS are poorly removed in conventional Wastewater Treatment Plants which limits circularity in the water cycle, for instance by complicating nutrients recovery from sewage sludge for fertiliser use. Up to date recommendations on choosing sludge treatment technologies to deliver 'PFAS free' fertilisers are missing. There is also currently no mass flow analysis of PFAS fate and degradation during sediment treatment for material recovery from dredged sediments. Insights on PFAS removal from these matrices (i.e. wastewater, sediments, sludge) will be addressed in the CWA. PFAS removal from drinking water is also important to consider since urban areas with semi-closed water cycles face challenges posed by legacy pollutants and high chemical concentrations when providing sustainable drinking water. The results on combined drinking water treatment, as well as on advanced wastewater treatment and landfill leachate treatment can/will be addressed in the CWA.

ZeroPM will develop innovative solutions for water and sludge, looking at both removal efficiency but also sustainability metrics for the solutions. These results will inform risk management efforts.

Scope of the proposed Workshop (planned area of application):

The planned Workshop defines best practices, solutions, and guidelines concerning the handling of PMT/vPvM substances, not only assessing their behaviour in the soil-sediment water system but also their possible prevention at the source as well as end-of-pipe solutions. These solutions are clustered into categories (e.g. prevention, detection, risk assessment, measures) in order to reach various stakeholders within the system. As part of the categorized solutions, a special focus is placed on the following five circular economy routes:

1. Semi-closed water cycle for drinking water supply
2. Wastewater reuse for agricultural irrigation
3. Nutrient and energy recovery from treated sludge for fertilisers
4. Material recovery from dredged sediment for eco-materials
5. Groundwater and soil remediation to protect water cycle

The planned Workshop is applicable to researchers, public authorities, water utility operators, or companies developing market-ready solutions.

Are the following aspects potentially affected?

YES

NO

Safety matters		<input type="checkbox"/> ³		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Management system aspects	<input type="checkbox"/> ⁴			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Conformity assessment aspects	<input type="checkbox"/> ⁵			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Security matters		<input type="checkbox"/> ⁶		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

<Add information/explanations to the points marked „yes“>

Theme related standardization Technical Bodies, standards or regulations, if applicable:

- ISO/TC 147 – Water Quality
 - ISO/TC 190 - Soil quality
 - ISO/TC 224 - Drinking water, wastewater and stormwater systems and services
 - ISO/TC 275 - Sludge recovery, recycling, treatment and disposal
 - ISO/TC 282 – Water reuse
 - CEN/TC 230 - Water analysis
 - CEN/TC 308 - Characterization and management of sludge
 - CEN/TC 444 - Environmental characterization of solid matrices
-
- prEN 17892: Water quality - Determination of the sum of perfluorinated substances (Sum of PFAS) in drinking water - Method using liquid chromatography/mass spectrometry (LC/MS)
 - ISO 21675: Water quality - Determination of perfluoroalkyl and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) in water - Method using solid phase extraction and liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS)

Optional attachments:

The Kick-off meeting is planned to be in February 2024.

Timescale	2023			2024										
	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP	OCT	NOV
Proposal form submission														
Project plan development														
Open commenting period for draft project plan														
Kick-off meeting														
CWA development														
CWA finalisation														
CWA publication														

³ For CEN: The CEN/CENELEC Workshop proposal shall be submitted to CEN/BT for decision. For CENELEC: Work on the proposed CEN/CENELEC Workshop shall not be initiated.

⁴ The CEN/CENELEC Workshop proposal shall be submitted to the CEN/CENELEC BT(s) for decision.

⁵ CEN/CENELEC Internal Regulations - Part 3, 33 applies.

⁶ For projects dealing with security matters the security risk analysis provided below (item 3) shall be carried out.

2 Proposal Form for the Workshop secretariat

CEN Workshop on "Soil-sediment-water system - Solutions to deal with PMT/vPvM substances"

Details of the Workshop secretary:

Name: Dr. Madlen Schmutde
Organization: Deutsches Institut für Normung e. V.
Postal address: Burggrafenstraße 6, 10787 Berlin, Germany
Email: madlen.schmutde@din.de
Phone: +49 30 2601-2763
Webpage: www.din.de

Finance:

European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program funded research project PROMISCES
Grant Agreement No.: 101036449.

Drafting and Dissemination:

The final CWA will be advertised on the websites of the R&I project PROMISCES as well as on the websites of the project partners to raise awareness. Moreover, the announcement of the CCMC website for the Kick-off of the CWA will be posted in PROMISCES social media as well as in partners social media to reach as many interested parties as possible.

Does the proposed CWA conflict with an EN or an HD?

	YES	NO
EN	<input type="checkbox"/> ⁷	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
HD (CENELEC)	<input type="checkbox"/> ⁷	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

<please add information/explanations to the points marked „yes“>

Is the proposed CWA within the domain of an existing CEN and/or CENELEC Technical Body?

- CEN/TC 230 - Water analysis
- CEN/TC 308 - Characterization and management of sludge
- CEN/TC 444 - Environmental characterization of solid matrices
- CEN/TC 165 - Waste water engineering
- CEN/TC 260 - Fertilizers and liming materials
- CEN/TC 248 - Textiles and textile products

CEN/CENELEC Management Centre (to be completed by CCMC):

Name of the CCMC project manager:

⁷ Work on the proposed CWA shall not be initiated.

Organization: CCMC

Postal address: Rue de la Science 23, 1040 Brussels

Email:

Phone: +32 2 550 xxxx

Webpage: <https://www.cencenelec.eu/aboutus/MgtCentre/Pages/default.aspx>

Response of identified potentially affected CEN/CENELEC TCs

	YES	NO	
Is there an active work item covering the scope of the planned CWA?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Are there arguments against the topic of the planned CWA?		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<Add information/explanations to the points marked „yes“>			

3 Security risk analysis

3.1 General

Security risk analysis is a process of identifying and analysing the main negative factors that may affect a standardization project's objectives. The following is targeted at secretariats of CEN/CENELEC Workshop Agreements (CWA) dealing with security issues. Its purpose is to help them identify and mitigate the risks associated with their project. It is structured around two main security threats that can affect the success of the work: major diverging interests among stakeholders and sensitive information.

3.2 Risk analysis on major diverging interest among stakeholders

Diverging interests among stakeholders can impede the process in reaching agreement on the CWA and even lead to failure to deliver the planned CWA. In order to identify and possibly mitigate the risks, the following questions should be reviewed:

- Is the planned CWA expected to have a major impact on the security policy/strategy of the core stakeholders?
- Does the scope of the CWA cover products or services with a clear dual-use purpose (i.e. which can be used for military purposes)?

3.3 Risk analysis on sensitive information

- In light of the scope of the CWA, is it likely that it may deal with sensitive information? If so, what is the information sensitivity level?
- Is there a need for a (non-)disclosure agreement?
- Is there any conflict of interest for stakeholders involved in the CEN/CENELEC Workshop, regarding especially the use they may make of any information they receive during the development of the CWA?
- What steps should be taken to manage information dissemination and storage (e.g. memory stick, emailing, storage) during the development process of the CWA?